

THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPEECH OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN WITH DISABILITIES THROUGH THE USE OF FINGER (SIGN LANGUAGE) IN EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES

Bakirova Umida Bakhtiyor kizi

Gulistan State University Faculty of Pedagogy 2nd year student

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ABSTRACT

Providing satisfactory education to children in primary grades is considered the main task of teachers. Finger learning is especially important for students with disabilities in inclusive education. This article is about the development of speech of preschool children with disabilities through the use of finger (sign language) in educational activities.

A child's lagging behind in educational and educational activities is the result of not mastering mental functions. For example, a child's discontinuity in putting on clothes is not due to a weak memory, but because he has not acquired the necessary skills to carry out this process. Along with the methods of psychoreaction of such a mental problem, the child can be presented with pictures showing how to put on clothes in the correct sequence. L.S. Vygotsky puts forward the idea that the health of the social environment is of primary importance for children with limited health opportunities. It also likens the development of children with disabilities to a plant with bad roots. "Its thin roots do not adapt to the layers and shape of the nutrient soil. They cannot reach the nutritious layers of the soil, and get into the dry and toxic layer. Such a plant could bloom under suitable conditions, but under normal conditions it did not reach the peak of development and withered. Therefore, it is appropriate to develop the educational system taking into account the specific aspects of each nation and people, national traditions, customs, goals and tasks of the state, and the mental and physical development of students. In the case of children with disabilities, if adults help the child's wishes and aspirations as much as possible without opposing the child's will and independence, the difficulties in the process of forming his personality will disappear by themselves. The appearance of stubbornness, stubbornness, and disobedience in a child with limited abilities occurs as a result of excessive manipulation by adults. Psychologist L.M. Krijanovskaya has extensively explained the ways of educating children with disabilities through psychological correction methods in the inclusive education system. In his opinion, the cooperation of school psychologist, pedagogue, educator and parents should be inextricably linked in order to be effective in the inclusive education system and to achieve good results.

To date, there are many problems and obstacles in the implementation of the inclusive education system on a global scale. They include: Negative attitude; Not being visible in the community; Financial problems; Physical adaptation; Number of students in the class;

Addiction; Discrimination based on sexual characteristics; Emergencies, conflicts and refugees. Negative attitude is probably the biggest obstacle for children with special needs to receive education in the system of general education institutions. The essence of the problem of negative attitude is that parents, community members, teachers, employees of general education institutions, management bodies, even children with special needs, are reluctant and do not want to receive education in their general educational institutions. The reason for this is people's misconceptions about disabled people, lack of information about them, the fact that disabled children grow up in a limited environment, etc. The essence of the problem of invisibility in the community is that many children with special needs are often locked up by their parents. They lock them up at home and do not show them to anyone, during the registration process no information is given about their disabled child. As a result, many disabled children are deprived of participation in society. The lack of any information about them leads to them not attending educational institutions.

The use of sign language has proven to be beneficial for children in a wide variety of settings. Teaching sign language to preverbal babies has proven to benefit children in their later years. Research shows that sign language speeds up speech development, reduces frustration in young children by giving them a means to express themselves before they know how to talk, increases parent-child bonding, and lets babies communicate vital information, such as if they are hurt or hungry. Infants who learn sign language also are thought to gain psychological benefits, such as improved confidence and self-esteem. Feelings of anger due to an inability to communicate may not occur as often. Having the ability to sign could be a lifesaver when a child is too flustered to speak clearly. It has been suggested that learning sign language can delay speech, but this is negated by experts who claim that in fact, it aids speech development. Most baby who can sign speak earlier than babies who do not learn sign language. Early exposure to signing helps infants to develop their language and reasoning skills. While others are still crying to get what they want, signing babies are learning how to communicate with words and simple phrases. Studies show long-term cognitive benefits, including:

- +12 IQ point advantage
- Accelerated speech and emotional development
- Enables children to communicate effectively
- Lowers frustration levels
- Improves child-parent bonding
- Reinforces the learning of educational concepts such as ABC's, animals, and other specific themes

In addition, children who know ASL score 17% higher on standardized tests administered in the younger school years than children who do not know sign language. Bilingualism of any languages (whether signed or spoken) is a great booster for brains. It enriches and enhances children's cognitive processes, leading to higher abstract and creative thinking, better problem-solving skills, greater cognitive flexibility, better listening skills, greater academic achievement, and much more. It also promotes cultural awareness, literacy, and other intellectual benefits. Another possible benefit of teaching a child to sign may be the facilitation of their attentiveness to social gestures of others as well as of themselves. It has

been seen over the years that teaching sign language to children with autism and other developmental disabilities does not interfere with learning to talk. In fact, teaching sign language along with speech has proven to speed up the development of spoken communication abilities. Parents of hearing children are discovering sign language is beneficial for children in a wide variety of situations. You can reinforce the signs your children learn at preschool by using them at home. The practice of teaching hearing children sign language will continue to gain popularity due to its many, many benefits. During preschool, kids experience structured time together that is both fun and educational. They learn how to bond with their peers, follow directions and stick to a schedule; all skills that prepare them for school. For children with special needs, there are certain pre-school activities that work particularly well to keep them engaged, focused and actively learning. Here are five suggestions that help children with special needs, both in the classroom and at home, get the most out of their learning experiences.

Principles of inclusive education: 1. Value of a person, his ability and does not depend on achievement. 2. Everyone has the ability to think and feel. 3. Every person has the ability to hear and communicate. 4. Everyone to each other in need 5. Full and real education of a person is possible only in real cooperation increases. 6. All people need the support of their peers. 7. Everyone It's not that they can't do something that keeps learners from achieving can do something. 8. Cooperation is a comprehensive human life increases. Includes educational institutions under the inclusive education system; pre-school and university, upper secondary education, secondary special vocational and higher education. The purpose of educational institutions is education and vocational training of children is to create an open learning environment by eliminating the barrier between them. Access to special programs and textbooks in comprehensive schools it won't happen. The inclusive education system is different from the integrated education system The content is distinguished by its essence, purpose, tasks and program of action.

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